

GENDER MAINSTREAMING IN A HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION (HEI)

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Abstract:

The study assessed the implementation of gender mainstreaming in government owned higher education institution in Eastern Visayas, Leyte, Philippines. It examined the level of awareness of school administrators and faculty members on gender mainstreaming initiatives and how they perceived about the extent of gender mainstreaming implementation in the areas of instruction, research, extension and production. The association between administrators and faculty attributes in terms of their awareness on the university's fourfold functions was also examined. The study was implemented through a descriptive and correlational survey research design utilizing a researcher made questionnaire which was pilot tested and standardized prior to actual conduct of the survey data gathering. Findings revealed that faculty members and administrators were moderately aware of the gender mainstreaming efforts of the university, but with significantly differs in their levels of awareness. By extent of implementation, gender mainstreaming was less implemented in the area of research, moderately implemented in the areas instruction, extension and production. Significant relationship was noted between designation and the level of awareness on gender mainstreaming, no statistical association was revealed among sex, age, academic rank and educational qualification. Meanwhile, age, academic rank and educational qualification were significantly related to instruction but not to research, both age and academic rank were significantly associated with extension and production. The HEI under study has complied with the mandated gender mainstreaming services delivery to its stakeholders, though facing some challenges along the implementation processes.

Keywords: gender mainstreaming, gender and development, higher education institutions, instruction, research, extension, production

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1. Introduction

Women throughout the world fought for their liberation from the bondage of oppression and exploitation. The triumphant years of women begun in 1975 when the United Nations declared it as the International Year for Women marking important changes in women's history. Development initiatives, social structures and policies emerged at the international and national arena. In the Philippines, the Philippine Commission for Women was created in 1975 serving as the lead agency in promoting gender equality (Philippine Commission on Women [PCW], 2009).

The 1987 Philippine Constitution was crafted to bring into reality the much desired legal and equality battle between and women as stipulated in Section 14, Article 11. Similarly, RA 7192 states that women and men are equal partners in development (GOP, 1991). To further institutionalize gender and development (GAD) efforts, Executive Order No. 273 was issued to state colleges and universities and government offices (Philippine Commission on Women [PCW], 1995). These policy guidelines make sure that gender mainstreaming in these government institutions are conducted. It likewise allows them to utilize at least five percent (5 percent) for GAD related projects and services in their total budget appropriations for GAD activities. Supporting this policy is CHED memorandum order 2015-01 promoting gender responsiveness and sensitivity in higher educational institutions in the Philippines (CHED, 2015).

Government owned universities have complied with the mandates in pursuing gender initiatives and gender mainstreaming. For more than a decade of GAD initiatives, an evaluation is deemed necessary to find out the attainment of the goals in gender mainstreaming as implemented by a government owned institution of higher learning.

The government which has the responsibility of promoting development for its people and ensure equitable distribution in a society used this GAD tool in program planning and its implementation. There is the notion that the government can initiate change toward a gender responsive development because it has the machinery and mechanisms for reaching out to people. These mechanisms could identify the needs of women and respond to their concerns thereby promoting effective participation. Likewise, the government has the resources and expertise to meet the social and economic demands (PCW, 2003).

The higher education schools, particularly government owned institutions of higher learning, serve as a potent avenue for change (Rodriquez and Abocejo, 2018). Khan et al. (2015) noted that institutions of higher learning over the world are deemed responsible for promoting honor among men and women. In essence, promoting gender mainstreaming in the education sector is undeniably an important development (Yang, 2016; Cuñado and Abocejo, 2018; Avila and Malquisto, 2019). Accordingly, Gurjar (2017) viewed education as one of the most effective tools in responding to challenges faced by nations and societies (Trazo and Abocejo, 2019; Jolejole-Caube, Dumlao and Abocejo, 2019). Educated women who have self-confidence, self-esteem and awareness make them better in life-decision making (Batoool et al., 2016; Abocejo et

al., 2012). The school, as an institution of learning, is where the individual is socialized, skills, values and attitudes are developed. The curriculum design, text books used, policies promulgated and other practices in school have significant effect to the learner.

It is then imperative that the school's vision, mission, goals and objectives through its policies, functions, programs and activities must inculcate gender responsiveness in the entire academic community (Abocejo and Padua, 2010; Avila and Malquisto, 2019). Promotion of a more gender sensitive educational goals, objectives, policies and programs must be pursued (Abocot and Añonuevo, 2015). As change agents, the administrators, teaching and non-teaching personnel who are gender sensitive and advocates for gender equality and women empowerment (Abocejo et al., 2012) will likewise transform individuals to become gender advocates; individuals who respect the rights of both men and women (Cerbito-Abocot, 2018).

In this light, this paper argues that assessing and determining the GAD efforts conducted by a HEI bring about better understanding and heightened awareness among employees and administrators in the implementation of GAD programs and initiatives encompassing the inherent fourfold functions of a University along instruction, research, extension and production.

1.1 Study Objectives

The study assessed the extent of gender mainstreaming implementation in a government owned University. Specifically, the study determined the (1) extent of implementation of gender mainstreaming along the following areas of instruction, research, extension and production, (2) level of awareness of the administrators and faculty members on gender mainstreaming, and (3) relationships between respondents' profile towards the extent of gender mainstreaming in the four areas of instruction, research, extension and production.

2. Literature Review

As a process, gender mainstreaming evaluates and assesses the implications for men and women of any course of action encompassing legal treaty, policy formulation, program planning and initiatives at all levels in any area of societal issues and concerns (Ramzan et al., 2015). As a strategy, gender mainstreaming enables men and women get involved in the essential dimensions of design, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of policies and programs in all political (Evangelio and Abocejo, 2015), economic (Abocejo, 2017) and societal spheres (Abocejo and Gubalane, 2012) where men and women benefit equally and inequality is halted (Abocejo et al., 2012). This is supported by Republic Act 9710 (Magna Carta for Women), which stipulates that gender mainstreaming should be included in designing, implementing, monitoring and evaluating policies and programs of both national and local government units (PCW 2015).

Zvinkliene (2016) stressed that gender mainstreaming takes a systematic account of the differences between the conditions and needs of both women (Alvarez, Ong and

Abocejo, 2017) and men in all the policies and actions during the post-industrial society. While Wittbom (2015) pointed out that in gender mainstreaming gender, the norms of society have to be examined. To investigate the norms prevailing in the society, it could be viewed as established habits of thought or as institutions (Almazan et al., 2019). Accordingly, Wittbom (2015) said that gender mainstreaming strategy could challenge the existing norm and this require for change. During the change process, gender awareness and open mindedness of all those people who obstruct in the reconstruction of this inequality could be done by bargaining new norms that establish gender equality in the organization (Wittbom, 2015; Abocot and Añonuevo, 2015).

Meanwhile, Meyer (2017) explained that schools must develop the personality and character that will eradicate traditional gender roles and norms existing in the society. Yang (2016) also argued that gender equality must be considered an aim in policy and educational practice. There are approaches in the study of gender equality policies (Ertan, 2016). The first approach focuses on one or small number of issues while the second approach focuses on a specific sector of government like representation and reproduction policies (Fernandez and Abocejo, 2014). On the other hand, the focus of the third approach is the international organizations like the United Nations.

According to Henry et al. (2017), there are conditions needed to successfully integrate gender equality perspective in organizations. These conditions include a *“clear vision with measurable indicators; strong, consistent and visible support; an approach which is deeply rooted in the organizational culture and competencies; ensures accountability at all levels and invest both financial and technical resources”* (Henry et al., 2017).

The Philippine Commission Women (2015) likewise, emphasized that gender mainstreaming is a means of modifying and enhancing organizational culture. This is supported by providing adequate financial resources, support mechanisms and procedures and committed personnel and officials who will be working towards a more humane, just and progressive society. There are five levels of gender mainstreaming presented by the PCW (2016) which includes the foundation formation where the agency commits GAD as a priority thrust in the organization; putting-up of strategic systems like the formation of Technical Working Groups and the implementers; the application of gender responsive plans through its programs and activities; the commitment and institutionalization and lastly, replication and innovation where GAD is fully integrated into the inherent functions of organizations and recognized as a model by other entities.

The head of agencies are usually the people who shoulders the task of gender mainstreaming, A focal for GAD is also established in the organization who take the lead in planning and evaluating policies and programs based agency’s thrust and needs of its members (Pañares and Abocejo, 2019). Likewise, they are responsible in data generation and management; and establishment of linkages and partnerships (PCW, 2002).

Women empowerment refers to all processes where women take control and ownership of their lives (Francina and Joseph, 2013; Abocejo et al., 2012). On the other hand, Ali et al. (2015) associated higher education of women with empowerment,

personal development (Trazo and Abocejo, 2019) and employment opportunities. Batool et al. (2016) concluded in their study that psycho-social factors such as self-esteem, husband support, social support and internal locus of control are significant in determining the empowerment of women.

Sachs (2013) noted that the goals of gender equality have not been met at the global level notwithstanding some progress in the aspects of women's participation in politics and business. Even if parents were supportive of their daughters' right to education, financial constraints and patriarchal norms (Abocejo, 2015a) are still seen as barriers towards female education at the university level (Ali et al. 2015).

In China, there is evidence of more women occupying managerial positions in schools and educational institutions at various levels of the bureaucracy, improving women's participation management and decision making in HEIs. Employed Chinese women are among the highest in the world, with about three of four women in the labor force (Attne, as cited in Zhao and Jones, 2017). Relatively however, few Chinese women move up to take senior leadership positions (as cited in Wang and Kai 2015). Vivek (2017) concluded that teachers at present time encounter less challenges in their jobs, yet they are not completely recognized as equal partners by their male counterparts.

Caglar (2013) likewise pointed out that as a result of gender mainstreaming, there were innovations made in certain procedures as well as in the organizations within a bureaucracy (Cerbito-Abocot, 2018) or even in private organizations. In Spanish universities, undergraduate gender and politics studies started to be introduced (Kantola and Lombardo, 2016). But feminists' scholars argued that in spite of gender mainstreaming, these changes have not successfully achieved equality (Caglar 2013). In fact, mainstreaming of gender (Squires, as cited in Wittbom, 2015) met some resistance (Kantola and Lombardo, 2016). The resistance can be both active and passive.

Ramzan et al. (2015) investigated the practices and strategies on the university's gender mainstreaming and reported that most of the male and female respondents contradicted that the university has a gender policy. Majority of them were not sure if there was an allocation of a specific budget for gender and categorically answered "no" on the routine conduct of gender analysis. Forty and nine percent likewise perceived that the university have no gender unit or focal system. Though there are advocates and experts on gender, 45.5 percent of the respondents believed that it did nothing.

Thobejane and Mogorosi (2017) revealed that gender mainstreaming in its functions met difficulties. Most strategic top positions in the university are still dominated by men while their female counterpart is still marginalized. They recommended the conduct workshops and conferences to promote awareness on gender issues (Tiauzon and Malquisto, 2019). Teachers who attended training on gender equity professional development were more likely to manifest a gender sensitive teaching behavior (Luongco, 2012; Avila and Malquisto, 2019).

These findings support other studies (Verloo, 2005; Verdonk, Mans, Lagro-Janseen, 2006; Wang 2010; Yang, 2016; Rodrigues and Abocejo, 2018; Abocejo et al.,

2012) which revealed that Gender Mainstreaming in the field of education have indicated that it would be a gradual process. There is complete institutional change occurs only when the idea has been internalized (Wittbom, 2015) and practiced (Tiauzon and Malquisto, 2019) by the members of the organization. This support the idea of Ottervik (2017) that gender equality does not only change women's lives but transform societies as well.

2.1 Theoretical Background

The study is anchored on the feminist theory advocated by Janet (1997) which argues that men and women should have equal political, economic and social rights and opportunities (Girls Life, 2015). It is also based on the idea of Tagore (Gurjar, 2017) that women should be equal partners of men in all fields, not superior nor subordinate. As such Ramzan (2015) considered equality of gender as the heart of sustainable world. Equality of gender prepares and strengthen sustainable development (Latham, 2007; Phillips, 2015).

Sustainable development is achieved when an individual or a community meets the need of the present generation without compromising the ability of the next generation to meet their own needs (Raborar, 2016; Abocejo, 2015b). In so doing, achieving gender equality and empowering all women and girls is one of the sustainable development goals (Abocejo et al. 2012). Two most important components of women's empowerment are women's education and employment (Larsen and Hollos, 2003; Grown et al., 2005, Abocejo et al., 2012).

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

Improving the education of women will increase the chance of employment and labor force participation resulting to more economic independence (Fernandez and Abocejo, 2014; Mason and Smith 2000; Thang and Anh, 2002; Kabeer, 2005). When the women are economically empowered (Abocejo et al., 2012) they will contribute to the wealth and well-being of their families and the nation (Blumberg, as cited in Amaldass and Gnanadev, 2016).

Morover, Gender and Development (GAD) promotes gender equality by giving each one opportunities in all development efforts. These efforts in promoting greater gender equality will also contribute to the overall development of human society (Amaldass and Gnanadev, 2016; Abocejo, 2015b). The GAD model is a strategy to reduce the gender disparity and to increase the participation of women (Abocejo et al., 2012) which promotes economic advancement (World Bank, as cited in Colisson, 2004; Inabangan, Garcia and Abocejo, 2019). It likewise promotes a positive bias for women and seeks to minimize or remove the social and economic constraints that prevent women from exercising their freedom of choice (Abocejo et al., 2012).

The study is likewise premised on the idea that the profile of the faculty and administrators such as age, sex, designation, academic rank and educational attainment influences gender mainstreaming implementation in the university's fourfold functions namely; instruction, research, extension and production and the level of awareness on gender mainstreaming efforts of the university. The conduct of an assessment on the gender mainstreaming awareness and implementation may provide inputs for an intervention scheme to improve gender mainstreaming in the university's policies and programs.

3. Research Methodology

The study employed the descriptive and correlational survey research design utilizing a researcher made questionnaire as main data gathering tool. Prior to the actual survey, a pilot test was conducted to standardize the survey research instrument. The study was implemented in a government owned university Tacloban City, Leyte province, eastern Philippines. The research respondents included school administrators and organic faculty members of the university main campus and external campuses.

The randomly chosen respondents were comprised of 66 university officials and 185 organic faculty members. Informed consents were taken from each respondent prior to the actual survey. The survey data were collated, processed and statistical summary were generated for analysis and interpretations to address the stated study objectives. Descriptive and correlational measures like the means, percentages and Pearson r were calculated for analysis and discussions of salient findings.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Profile of research respondents

By gender, there was almost the same proportion between male (49.40 percent) and female (50.60 percent) respondents indicative of a fair gender distribution of the entire research respondents (n=251). Over one-fourth (27.49 percent) of the respondents were middle aged (39-47 years) followed by middle adults (48-56 years) with nearly one-fifth (19.52 percent) as young adults. On the extreme side, young and adult groups were of the same proportion at 13.15 percent apiece. Indicatively, the teaching profession is now equally enjoyed by both genders which were traditionally assigned to women.

By school designation, forty-six were coordinators, twenty-two were unit heads, fifteen directors, four college deans and three vice-presidents. The largest proportion (64.14 percent) was organic faculty members without any designation. More than half (53.78 percent) instructors while a little over one-fourth (26.70 percent) had academic rank of Assistant Professors. Notwithstanding long years of rendered services, their academic rank was still low which could be attributed to their educational qualifications because most of them were not masters or doctorate degree holders.

There is a need for them pursue and finish their graduate studies to qualify for higher academic rank. Majority of them may have been in the teaching career for quite a long time since more than one-fourth of them were middle aged followed by middle adults. The Associate Professors comprised about 13.94 percent with just 5.58 percent of the entire respondents holding full professorial ranks. More one-third (37.85 percent) were bachelor's degree graduates with units at the masters level. A little over one-fourth (26.69 percent) had masters degrees with doctorate units. Only about 16 percent were doctorate degree holders.

4.2 Extent of gender mainstreaming implementation along instruction, research, extension and production

The basic function of higher education is to teach, engage in research, to deliver community services and production. The interrelationship of the four functions creates the culture and climate of an academic institution.

Table 1: Extent gender mainstreaming implementation in the four-fold functions of instruction, research, extension and production

Functions	Faculty		Administration	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
Instruction	2.80	Moderately Implemented	2.85	Moderately Implemented
Research	2.32	Slightly Implemented	2.53	Moderately Implemented
Extension	2.76	Moderately Implemented	2.89	Moderately Implemented
Production	2.71	Moderately Implemented	2.57	Moderately Implemented
Grand Mean	2.65	Moderately implemented	2.71	Moderately Implemented
Ranges for the Weighted Mean Description				
1.00 -	1.80	Not implemented		
1.81 -	2.60	Slightly implemented		
2.61 -	3.40	Moderately implemented		
3.41 -	4.20	Highly implemented		
4.21 -	5.00	Very highly implemented		

4.2.1 Extent of Gender Mainstreaming along Instruction

Table 1 shows that gender mainstreaming was perceived to be moderately implemented by the faculty and administration groups. Instruction are principally carried out to strengthen faculty development, instructional materials and facilities development, sound and relevant curricula, and improved library facilities and resources to produce better of graduates.

Notably, the much implemented programs in instruction is the offering of courses traditionally for men are offered to women students, mean values of 3.66 for the

faculty and 3.73 for the administrators. This is evident in the institution report of school year 2006-2007 where out of four hundred sixty Engineering graduates, one hundred seventy-five (175) are females. This implies that students in the university, male or female can enroll in any course of their choice. Offering of subject on GAD is less implemented, a mean of 2.47 (faculty) and 2.37 (administrators), and the production of modules/resource GAD materials, a mean of 2.40, was likewise the less implemented. This implies that a review and revision of curricular offerings is needed.

The findings also reveal that *“Integration of gender issues and concerns in the curriculum,” “Use of non-sexist language in Instruction,” “Books and reading materials related to GAD are available in the library,” “Conduct of gender sensitivity seminars/trainings to students”* among others were moderately implemented. These may imply that the integration of GAD programs in the curriculum has yet to be improved in the HEI under study. As noted, the HEI under study offers courses in gender and development, peace education and arts appreciation under the economics program. This also connotes that more seminars and trainings related to gender and development are to be conducted both for the faculty and students to increase gender sensitivity. Trainings for teachers are essential because they are role models and agents of change both in school and in the community.

4.2.2 Extent of Gender Mainstreaming along Research

Gender mainstreaming in research is moderately implemented (Table 1) with weighted mean of 2.83 (moderately implemented) as assessed by the administrators, and less implemented as perceived by the faculty (weighted mean = 2.32). This disparity in the perceived extent of implementation of research between the administrators and faculty could be attributed to the lesser number of teaching loads of the administrators as compared to the rank and file faculty members. Administrators have less time in instruction tasks giving them time to do research. Moreover, they have higher level awareness than the faculty members about gender mainstreaming (Table 1). Such knowledge could influence them in the conduct gender related researches.

Publication of research outputs in local, regional and national peer reviewed papers and the presentation of gender research are likewise less implemented for both faculty and administrators. This implies that publication of researches is one of the weaknesses of along the area of research. Hence, there is a need to improve skills in research writing and publication. Since research is less implemented by the faculty, it implies that there is a need to increase their motivation to conduct gender related researches. Lorenzana (2003) reported that one of the approaches to motivation is needs satisfaction. It believes that satisfied worker is productive worker and that, management, should aim to identify ways of satisfying them. Hence, the needs of the faculty and administrator along research must be identified. The improvement in research performance is in compliance to RA 7722 which mandates higher education institutions in the Philippines to enhance the research functions.

4.2.3 Extent of Gender Mainstreaming along Extension

Philippine Republic Act 9311 stipulates that the university shall undertake extension services. Implementation of gender mainstreaming in Extension services got overall mean values, 2.76 and 2.89, interpreted as moderately implemented for faculty and administrators respectively as reflected in Table 1. The programs and activities which got the highest mean value, 3.32, perceived by the administrators are the skills trainings provided to both men and women beneficiaries followed by programs and projects that increase productivity among male and female clientele in the communities a mean value of, 3.18, perceived by the administrators. This implies that the university has served the women and men better in the communities through the skills development program of the extension services.

On the other hand, assisting clients who suffered from various forms of violence and abuse got the lowest mean values, 2.53 and 2.57 for faculty and administrators respectively. This implies that the faculty and administrators rarely encounter clients suffering from violence or other forms of abuse. It is understandable to rarely encounter clients suffering domestic violence because the faculty and administrators work with people in the communities in short period of time.

The clients, women and men alike, have to develop trust and confidence before they could confide in their personal problems to someone. It has been reported that the most common form of violence is between husband and wife. This has been acknowledged to exist for some time and to a certain degree but has been tolerated as part of married life. A woman who has been abused, beaten, or assaulted by her husband usually tolerates such behavior from him because of her socialization and belief in her traditional woman's role (Salcedo et al., 2001). It is in this context that cases of violence may not be reported to the members of the academe while conducting extension activities in the community.

Among the other programs moderately implemented by both administrators and faculty members are programs/projects that increase productivity among male and female clientele in the communities, assistance that respond to the health needs of male and female beneficiaries, Based on the annual reports, the university has provided services that benefit both men and women in the community through livelihood skills training program, medical and dental services among others. However, the findings imply there is a need to improve services to the less fortunate members of the community. The university has its mandate to serve the people in the community to help them achieve better quality life. This is in support to one of the thrusts of the CHED which is the strengthening of research and extension functions of Higher Education Institutions (Javier et al., 2002).

4.2.4 Extent of Gender Mainstreaming along Production

Generation of income is one the functions of government universities. These universities engage in income generating activities to augment their financial requirements in running the academic institutions. Table 1 reflects the findings on the extent of gender mainstreaming in production. As revealed, both the faculty, a mean

value of 2.71, and administrators, a mean value of 2.67, have moderately implemented production. Preparation of project proposal for an income generating activity was moderately implemented by both faculty and administrators with mean values of 2.79 and 2.84 respectively. On-going income generating activity by the faculty was likewise moderately implemented by both respondents. Formulation of policy guidelines regarding the implementation of income-generating projects got mean values, 2.77 and 2.67 for faculty and administrators, respectively interpreted as moderately implemented. Likewise, attendance in orientation regarding the implementation of income generating projects got the mean values 2.70 (faculty) and 2.65 (administrators) interpreted as moderately implemented. These findings imply that both the faculty and administrators are not fully involved in the income generation projects of the university. This indicates that production is not the primary function of an academic institution. Villena et al. (2015) noted that the role of an academic institution is to prepare individuals toward their functional and proactive roles in society. It is likewise essential for education to be active in analyzing the needed skills for the industry and business sectors. Dagle et al. (2015) likewise pointed out that the purpose of education is to help individuals become competent in communications and productivity through the programs implemented based on their needs and differences.

4.3 Level of Awareness of School Administrators and Faculty Members on Gender Mainstreaming Efforts

As reflected in Table 2, the respondents are moderately aware on gender mainstreaming efforts of the university, an overall mean of 2.75 and 3.24, for faculty and administrators respectively. Among the faculty, there are forty-five and sixty three percent (45.63 percent) of them who are moderately aware, thirty-three and one percent (33.01 percent) slightly aware and five and thirty-four percent (5.34 percent) not aware at all. It is observed that the administrators have better awareness on gender mainstreaming in the university than the faculty as reflected on the table.

Table 2: Level of awareness on gender mainstreaming among the University faculty and administrators

Level of Awareness	Faculty		Administrators	
	Frequency	Percent (%)	Frequency	Percent (%)
Very much aware	3	1.46	1	2.27
Aware	30	14.56	15	34.1
Moderately aware	94	45.63	17	38.63
Slightly aware	68	33.01	11	25.00
Not aware at all	11	5.34	-	-
Total	206	100.00	44	100.00
Grand Mean (Interpretation)	2.75 (Moderately Aware)		3.24 (Moderately Aware)	
Ranges for the Weighted Mean	Description			
1.00 - 1.80	Not aware			
1.81 - 2.60	Slightly aware			
2.61 - 3.40	Moderately aware			
3.41 - 4.20	Highly aware			
4.21 - 5.00	Very highly aware			

The largest group (38.63 percent) of the administrators are moderately aware, followed by thirty-four and one percent (34.1 percent) who are aware and but no one is unaware (Table 3). This implies that administrators have been given more opportunities to attend trainings and seminars related to gender and development; as such they are more aware with the current issues, laws and programs of the government particularly in the University. However, the entire academic community, particularly the faculty, must enhance their awareness to help improve gender mainstreaming in the whole university system.

Findings revealed that study respondents are aware (mean = 4.05) of women in the University occupying strategic positions. Indeed, many of the top level positions in the university are handled by women. However, in terms of budget utilization for Gender and Development, both respondents are slightly aware, mean scores of 2.23 and 2.50, for faculty and administrators respectively. This implies the both faculty and administrators are not well informed in the GAD budget utilization in the university.

4.4 Relationships among respondents' profile towards the extent of gender mainstreaming along instruction, research, extension and production

Table 3: Relationships among respondents profile towards the extent of gender mainstreaming implementation along instruction, research, extension and production

Key Independent Variable	Instruction		Research		Extension		Production	
	r-value	p-value	r-value	p-value	r-value	p-value	r-value	p-value
Sex	-0.107 ^{ns}	0.091	-0.140 [*]	0.029	-0.118 ^{ns}	0.066	-0.121 ^{ns}	0.058
Age	-0.173 ^{**}	0.006	-0.031 ^{ns}	0.627	-0.244 ^{**}	0.0001	-0.237 ^{**}	0.0002
Designation	-0.045 ^{ns}	0.477	-0.098 ^{ns}	0.128	-0.073 ^{ns}	0.255	0.007 ^{ns}	0.910
Academic Rank	-0.130 [*]	0.040	0.025 ^{ns}	0.704	-0.150 [*]	0.019	-0.214 ^{**}	0.001
Educational Qualification	-0.137 [*]	0.031	0.101 ^{ns}	0.118	0.223 ^{ns}	0.223	-0.121 ^{ns}	0.058

ns – Not significant, * - Significant at $\alpha < 0.05$, ** - Highly significant at $\alpha < 0.01$

4.4.1 Relationships between the extent of gender mainstreaming implementation and instruction

On the other hand, the test of significant relationship between instruction and the selected profile of the respondents revealed that instruction has a negative correlation with age, academic rank and educational qualification (Table 3). The inverse relationship indicates that as these three variables progress over time, the engagement levels of the University faculty and administrators tend to slow down. This further suggest that age, academic rank and educational qualifications have some bearing on the extent of implementation on gender mainstreaming in Instruction.

Accordingly, the older the teacher becomes and higher the educational achievements attained, the lower is the performance on gender mainstreaming in Instruction. When the teacher becomes older, the interest in attending gender related seminars/trainings or the production of modules may decrease. Most probably, there had been enough trainings, seminars or had been actively involved in producing modules during his/her younger years.

This is likewise true with educational qualifications. When the teacher's educational achievement rises, there is the possibility that administrative position is given resulting to a decrease in responsibilities related to instruction. On the other hand, designation does not affect Instruction. As such, Instructors having designated positions may have same performance in the implementation of gender mainstreaming with those who have no position. Though they have better awareness on gender mainstreaming as reflected in Table 13, their performance is the same with other faculty members without administrative positions.

Likewise, sex does not have significant relationship with instruction. This means that the teaching performance related to gender does not vary with female instructors. Both male and female instructor may have the same interest in discussing gender issues and concerns because they could easily relate these to their actual experiences or observations happening in the society.

This may contradict to the findings of Goodwin and Stevens (as cited in Hill, 2014) on the influence of gender on faculty perceptions of good teaching. Findings revealed that there are gender differences on faculty perceptions and that women showed higher mean average than men professors on few characteristics of good teaching as follows concern about improving students' higher order thinking; concern about students' improving self-esteem; encourage student interaction via small group activities; and seeking a variety of learning levels exams and discussions.

4.4.2 Relationships between the extent of gender mainstreaming implementation and research

It is noted that no significant relationship exists between research and age, designation, academic rank and educational qualifications (Table 3). The finding suggests that among young and old instructors, being an administrator or a mere faculty member, bachelor or masters' degree graduates, their performance in research will be on the same level. However, a significant relationship is noted between research and sex of the respondents as reflected in Table 3. This indicates that male faculty performs research differently than their female counterpart. This may indicate that female faculty member may be more interested in doing gender related researches than male faculty members. Greater interest among female faculty may be manifested because the subject of study is usually women whom the female faculty members are comfortable with.

4.4.3 Relationships between the extent of gender mainstreaming implementation and extension

Findings show that the implementation of extension is inversely and highly associated with age and academic rank (Table 3). This implies that the older the faculty member becomes, the lesser is the engagement in extension activities. Age matters in one's interest to perform extension works. Younger faculty members have more vigor and energy. They love new and challenging experiences which extension work offers. Likewise, those with higher academic rank may have been long in the service and have been actively involved in extension programs and activities during their prime years.

So that as they go up in the academic ranking, the less they involve in extension activities. Moreover, those with higher academic rank may have lost interest in participating extension activities because they may have reached the highest number of points in extension for their faculty performance evaluation. Since their involvement in extension may not give them extrinsic benefit, their involvement diminishes and cannot provide extension services as much as those who are still earning points for ranking and evaluation. It is also possible that those with higher academic rank are given administrative positions. In effect, their administrative functions and responsibilities may limit them to conduct extension activities. Hence, age and academic rank affect the implementation of gender-related extension programs.

4.4.3 Relationships between the extent of gender mainstreaming implementation and production

The extent of gender mainstreaming implementation in relation to production reveals that it is highly but inversely associated with age and academic rank (Table 3). These findings suggest that the older faculty members become, the lesser is their involvement in income-generating activities in the University. Similarly, those with higher academic rank may perform less in income-generating activities. It appears that older faculty members and administrators are less likely interested in engaging in income-generating activities because they have already sufficient earnings to meet their needs. Besides, they may have higher salaries and may no longer be spending for the education of their children. Meanwhile, younger faculty members need more financial resources to support their needs especially if they have young and schooling children. Accordingly, those with higher academic ranks are no longer interested in generating income in school like the production of modules. The younger ones who may have higher financial needs are more likely to engage in income-generating activities.

On the contrary, other profile characteristics of the respondents like sex, designation and educational qualifications, did not yield significant relationships with production (Table 3). In like manner, designations and educational qualifications of the study respondents did not significantly correlate with their involvement in production activities as one of their major functions in the University.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

Gender mainstreaming in the HEI under study still faces some challenges. Though it has complied with the mandate of gender mainstreaming in its functions, there is a need to strengthen its implementation through its gender-responsive policies, plans and programs in instruction, research, extension and production. Improvement of the university's gender mainstreaming needs strong commitment and support from the administrative officials as well as the employees specifically on the area of research. A study may be conducted to determine the factors why there was less implementation along this area by the faculty.

Likewise, trainings and seminars may be conducted to increase the level of awareness on gender mainstreaming among the administrators and faculty. More importantly, increase awareness on GAD budget allocation is necessary for them to plan and implement gender responsive programs and projects like the conduct gender researches. Gender responsive programs and projects of the university and community it serves require sufficient budget allocation for its successful implementation. Hence, the need for the administrative and financial support.

About the Author

Luz S. Ilagan is an Associate Professor V of the Eastern Visayas State University (EVSU) where she has continually served for more than three decades. She has been a forerunner of EVSU Community Extension Services Office, head of the Social Sciences and Economics Department, and a Gender and Development advocate. She completed her PhD in Educational Program Management, Master in Education major in Administration and Supervision and completed a Bachelor's Degree in Social Work. Her research interests are in gender and development studies, educational management and social work.

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